

Restructuring in the Neighborhood of Guet Ndar-Senegal

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Abstract— In the recent history, Guet Ndar development planning has caused problems of poverty, land use, housing and infrastructure in the cities, the scale and intensity of urban problems, which the developing countries in Africa, including Senegal, are phenomena that arise with much more acute.

These problems are, to a large extent, population growth, the severe shortage and economic uncertainty of resources that can be devoted to investment, particularly for urban basic services, social housing and the development of the living environment.

There is also the fact that, for a long time, the development strategies are focused on rural development in logic of most interventionist who came to independence. Unfortunately, in many cases, this approach to the development of the rural sector has not achieved the expected results and the urban centers were the first victims of poor performance.

In Senegal, the government tried to restructure the habitat areas for years without achieving the objectives set. In Guet Ndar, for example, the population believes that it has not always been associated with projects on the neighborhood, which caused some rejection and failure. Today, in order to reclaim the space of Guet Ndar, it is imperative to be in collaboration with the population to restructure, to find spaces to rehouse the surplus population, to create basic infrastructures and to reorganize the fishing activity.

Keywords— restructure, development, decentralization, planification, infrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

In collaboration with the MDA and the District Council (DC), we conducted a "requalification and redevelopment of Guet Ndar" neighborhood, which is part of the priority programs of the new municipal team. Within the framework of decentralization, the town council has as its mission conception, programming and the implementation of the actions of economic, educational, social and cultural development of regional, communal or rural interest[1].

Thus, in order to ensure a harmonious urban and socio-economic development of the neighborhood and to ensure a better living environment for the population, it is necessary for the municipality, in collaboration with the District Council

(DC) to reorganize by making coherent management choices for different land uses (activities, habitat, facilities, infrastructures, etc.) It was in this context that we were asked to conduct a study during our internship at the CDA on the redevelopment and re-qualification of Guet Ndar.

Law 96-07 defined nine areas of competence transferred to local authorities [2], including: town planning and housing, land use planning and the environment. In this respect, local authorities have the prerogatives to carry out all policies aimed at addressing the concerns of populations in these areas.

The municipality of Saint-Louis, within the framework of this policy of managing the concerns of the populations, envisages a number of projects, including the redevelopment of Guet Ndar, aimed at improving the framework and living conditions of the population.

The redevelopment of Guet Ndar, by the wish of the population, is also stipulated in various documents, in particular the Master Plan of Urbanism (MPU) of Saint-Louis horizon 2025.

All the possibilities of special development of this district are rendered impossible because of its natural limits. These are constituted on one hand by the water of the Senegal River and the Atlantic Ocean towards the mouth and on the other hand by the cemetery and on the north by the district of Ndar Tout.

This district has been the subject of several studies because of its specificity with a high density about 2,200 inhabitants per km², which is almost 50 times the regional average [3] and buildings that ignore urban planning standards, which is unexpected for the visitors.

Intensification results from the fact that the neighborhood has no possibility of extension (being stuck between the small arm of the St. Louis River and the Atlantic Ocean) and the reluctance of its inhabitants for any de-escalation action in the past. Attempts to restructure by the State have been doomed to failure, as most of the holders of plots have sold their land and have remained in the neighborhood.

The majority of the population is fishermen and the population where there are two fishermen per household [4], has always wanted to stay in the neighborhood in order not to leave the sea: their main place of activity. This activity, which requires a great deal of effort, strengthens the fishermen in the choice of a large family.

Moreover, it should be noted that the tradition of the fishermen of this locality means that in a family, from the grandfather to the grandson, almost all men are fishermen. Thus, all the occupations carried out by the inhabitants are directed towards the capture, processing or marketing of fishery products. The street has become a backyard for the inhabitants and a space for various activities, especially for the fishing industry.

Objectives of the study

This study and research work is part of the dynamics of the studies linked to the improvement of the inhabitants' living environment and the image of the Guet Ndar neighborhood by means of an urban redevelopment operation which must integrate several dimensions (Urban, social and spatial).

The project aims to maintain a large number of people who live in the neighborhood and facilitate their access to land and basic infrastructure, the decongestion of the neighborhood by rehousing a large number of households to reduce the degree of promiscuity with its consequences on health and well-being.

The ultimate objective of the development of the neighborhood is to improve the living environment and the living conditions of the population by access to the minimum basic service.

Hypothesis

The neighborhood of Guet Ndar because of its population and its high density encounters enormous difficulties. Guet Ndar can be rehabilitated thanks to the collaboration of the various development actors of the neighborhood and the population through the neighborhood council.

Methodology

In order to carry out this work, we after a documentary review, we have carried out investigations with the neighborhood council, municipal services (MDA, Health Service, etc.) The Water Company and other organizations that work in the same issues as CIDG (Convention for Integrated Development of Guet Ndar) and the population. The process consists mainly of the following phases:

At the beginning we conducted a documentary review in order to situate the geographical context of our study and to present the human environment and economic activities through the neighborhood of Guet Ndar. This involved conducting semi-structured interviews and interviews with the DC (District Council), development partners and the population.

Interviews with the DC focused mainly on the development of the neighborhood with particular emphasis on the action of the various Basic Community Organisations. With regard to development partners, the interviews focus mainly on the

constraints and development opportunities of the neighborhood. This allowed us to draw up a state of play in terms of development; Sanitation and density and to assess the consistency and relevance of the data collected in relation to our research objectives.

II. PRESENTATION OF THE DISTRICT

Saint-Louis neighborhood located on the Langue de Barbarie (strip of land between the Atlantic Ocean and the small arm of the Senegal River), Guet Ndar stretches for about a kilometer (from Pointe à Pitre to The descent of the Moustapha Malick Gaye bridge in the north, to the fishing wharf in the south) and two hundred and fifty meters in its greatest breadth (from the small arm to the ocean).

With an area of about 250,000m² (25 ha or 0.25 Km²), Guet Ndar has a population of about 55,000 inhabitants, ie an average density of 2,200 inhabitants / km², more than 50 times the regional average [5]. It is the most populated district of Saint-Louis. It is home to an average of 13% of the population of Saint-Louis. Guet Ndar is 90% wolof-populated, and is also the most homogeneous St. Louis district. Saturated and occupied in its smallest entities, the space available for the streets and habitats is very limited since, in its greatest width, the littoral cordon does not exceed 250 meters. On the north-south axis there are eleven transverse streets connecting the beach and the riverbank. The plan of the neighborhood is thus theoretically orthogonal, but the habitat has invaded the congested tracks of reformed canoes, cattle with ties, nets (fishing or drying clothes).

The climate is semi-temperate, strongly influenced by the sea and river winds. The wind and the marine climate do not favor the development of rich, varied and abundant vegetation. With the exception of its southern coastline, where filaos and salt-resistant herbaceous plants develop, Guet Ndar has practically no trees and green spaces.

The dominant activities at Guet Ndar remain mainly fisheries and related activities, where there are two fishermen per household. The occupation of public roads and certain open spaces by activities, particularly those related to fishing, is a real problem and needs to be addressed.

Considered the oldest district in the city of Saint-Louis, Guet Ndar is enameled by many controversies as to its edification. However, we note the following:

The neighborhood was created two centuries before the discovery of the town of Saint-Louis by ADJ (title given to those who did the pilgrimage in Mecca) tribes located near the mouth of the Falémé, 100 km from Nouakchott whose immigration ended at Guet Ndar precisely at the current location of the Ndeugueur mosque.

Concerning the name of Guet Ndar, it would come according to the most known and most recent version of Guet" meaning pasture and "Ndar [6] designating Saint-Louis.

There are many unfortunate major events that have marked the evolutionary process of the neighborhood. There are a few:

- 1914 - 1915 and 1929: Epidemics of plague, which had decimated part of the population and caused a massive displacement to reclassification areas as well as the burning of the district;
- 1914: Project of development of Guet Ndar by commander JAFFREY;
- 1920 - 1921: Revival without success of this plan;
- 1950: The most repeatable catastrophic flood that caused a loss of human life;
- 1978: Cholera outbreak leading to deaths

The settlement of Guet Ndar is the result of an evolutionary process favored by a multitude of migratory movements, particularly those from outside to the interior of the neighborhood. The inhabitants of the South district had left their locality for Guet Ndar following a decree of the Colonial Governor. Populations of the Cayor, the Baol, the Sine and even the Djollof ethnics, who fled from the insecurity and hunger, followed them.

The spatial development of Guet Ndar is marked by three main stages: the first concerns the massive arrival of Walo walo and Cayorian seasonal populations and Moorish tanners who resided in Goxu Mbaac; the second stage was marked by technical operations called "seuk"; the third is characterized by movements of decongestion and disengagement towards the hydrobase and Goxu Mbaac [7].

III. MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

Guet Ndar, despite regular layout with two penetrating a main north / south, about 15 meters high, one of about 10 meters north / south) and a ridge along the arm, separated by channels (about 10 meters, 100 meters) suffered from overcrowding.

The neighborhood is now at the forefront of the company, with a good management of the space), a lack of basic infrastructure, to ensure the minimum living conditions and a lack of sanitation, among other issues, which have a negative impact on the health and hygiene conditions of space and consequently for the population.

The development of Guet Ndar space revolves around a central question: "Who is the cause of uncontrolled occupation of public space which is very small (in the absence of a zone of extension) and despised by the population?"

The intensity of the canoe river and sea banks and the use thereof for the conversion of fish products, the display of fishing nets on the road are all factors that increase the dimensions of the quality of life.

In 1972, the district was taken at sidewalk stands. Today, there are three roads to watch the river boulevard of Guet Ndar, which was covered by the funding of the World Bank, and two cross roads located in the southern part of the neighborhood. In addition, the side of ship-refrigerated trucks has also been taken by the French cooperation.

The existence of the traditional coating (buried) is located on the main road to prevent infiltration of rainwater and promotes its accumulation at a superficial level, compounded in many areas and preventing the movement of people and vehicles. In many cases, the maximum width of the streets can access to emergency vehicles and municipal services (garbage), which represents a risk to the population and contributes to the deterioration of the neighborhood.

The district of Guet Ndar lacks sewage, excreta and rainwater pipes in an adjoining urban environment. The subsoil is heavily contaminated by the use of a cesspool and traditional latrines. Septic tanks are always constructed with inadequate materials and in many cases suffer losses or penetration of water. This situation makes Guet Ndar a highly vulnerable area in the face of epidemics caused by:

Heavy rains result in an increase in the water table which increases the level of fecal matter contained in the septic tanks, latrines or wells to the surface and therefore inside the houses. About 55.74% of the neighborhood's population reported having suffered flooding in their home, of which 36.30% is related to the water table, and 48.15% to rainwater [8]. 48% of homes do not have a system of disposal. The pits are not built properly.

The lack of space has a negative influence on the living conditions of the population, according to a house and service sharing between different families. The lack of space, the deficiency and poor sanitary conditions of the housing construction quality, determine the parameters of the existing low livability.

For sanitation, the cooperation with the Convention for the Integrated Development of Guet Ndar was one of consolidation of its field of action. But with the complexities of National Sanitation Office of Senegal to refocus its activities and the work today in the establishment of a center for women's Guet Ndar processing.

The houses of Guet Ndar have a highly damaged condition in the majority of cases, especially areas intended for humid rooms, personal hygiene, and evacuation of excreta or kitchen water. These houses lack rooms for toilets, and use "pots of water" which they keep in places intended for shower or in courts, and which are emptied periodically on the river or the

sea. Another alternative is the use of the river's edge or the beach as a toilet.

It should also be noted that drinking water (90%) and electricity exist practically at the level of all the houses in Guet Ndar. But, although homes have a connection to the water supply network, 98% of the time [9], this is not intended for personal hygiene. Also, power system installations are not well executed or are non-compliant.

IV. PRESENTATION OF THE MUNICIPAL DEVELOPMENT AGENCY

The Municipal Development Agency is a non-profit organization which plays an important role in the implementation of strategies for the management of the city in terms of social engineering and urban management work in support of projects and programs in urban areas. It engages in a dynamic of institutional strengthening and thus ensures a mission of studies, advice, monitoring and coherence of actions and projects at the municipal level.

At the methodological level, the MDA adopts a local development approach based on active and interactive subsidiarity, which is articulated on a double scale: the city and the neighborhood. This original approach is thus global and transversal, focusing on an integral development of the entire urban space and affects all sectors of activity. Thus, it is primarily positioned as a place for exchanges, meetings and dialogue where all the actors of the city (local elected official, technician and civil society) can work in a concerted way to its development.

One initiative in Senegal, the Municipal Development Agency was established in 2000, the reform of the Coordination, Information and Outreach Activities in the Local Development itself was created in 1994 with the support of partners and of decentralized cooperation. This innovative experience was crowned internationally in 2000 in Windhoek, South Africa, where the Commune of Saint-Louis won the African trophy.

With more than 10-year experience, the Municipal Development Agency, within the limits of the tasks assigned to it by the General Assembly and the Board of Directors, provides important support to the Saint-Louis Commune. It then becomes a unique structure in sub-Saharan Africa by its status and the originality of its approach, based on broad consultation, genuine participation of people in the management of their living environment and coordination of all interventions on the communal territory.

Municipal Development Agency's approach takes place at the neighborhood level (with district councils) and at the communal level (urban planning, solid waste management, promotion of local economic development). The Agency assists the municipality in its role as client, in particular by

defining urban policies and projects and urban planning processes. As such, it is responsible for:

- Carry out the thoughts and studies likely to promote economic and social development, the development and the environment of the municipality of Saint Louis.

- Provide support and advice to the common in the design of municipal programs, plans and projects in a coordinated approach of the participatory approach;

- To ensure the follow-up and monitoring of the implementation of local development projects for the municipality.

The four directions are:

- The management of local development (neighborhood councils, collection of garbage, development areas and culture);

- The management of major projects, housing, sanitation, environment, sanitation, transport, etc.);

- The planning department.

- The management of community / private sector partners.

V. PRESENTATION OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD COUNCIL

The Neighborhood Council is a federative structure recognized by the municipality as a framework for the promotion of citizenship and local democracy, a space for consultation and coherence between actions and actors around neighborhood development issues. Set up in the framework of the Program to Strengthen and Support the Development of the City, community councils are a federal association of informal associations present in an area. The associations represented there are social, educational, religious, or commercial. This is clearly a social mix of a complete representation of the peoples of the area.

National coordination and consistency of actions and actors on development problems of the district, the district council is a federal structure recognized by the municipality, a framework for the promotion of citizenship and democracy at the local level. Its main objectives are:

- Bring together the neighborhood associations around the neighborhood's development issues;

- Encourage and / or support the self - promotion initiatives developed in the neighborhood, in relation to the municipal authorities residing in the neighborhood (Councilors and District Delegates);

- Contribute to the realization of the projects and actions identified within the framework of the District Development Plan, developed with the support of the Program to Strengthen and Support the Development of the City, which must ensure its articulation with the Communal Development Program; to constitute the privileged interlocutor for any intervention related to development actions in the neighborhood.

VI. PROBLEM ANALYSIS

The district of Guet Ndar lacks sewage, excreta and rainwater pipes in a contiguous urban environment. The basement is highly contaminated by the use of a pit and traditional latrines. Septic tanks are always constructed with inadequate materials and in many cases suffer losses or penetration of water. This situation makes Guet Ndar a highly vulnerable area in the face of epidemics caused by:

-Heavy rainfall resulting in an increase in the water table which increases the level of fecal matter contained in septic tanks, latrines or wells to the surface, and therefore inside houses. About 55.74 percent of the neighborhood's population reported having suffered flooding in their home, of which 36.30 percent was water-related, and 48.15 percent was rainwater [10].

-48% of homes do not have an excreta disposal system.

-Pits are not properly constructed.

The lack of space negatively affects the living conditions of the inhabitants, forcing to share a house and services between different families. The lack of space, the deficit in the sanitary condition of the dwellings and the poor quality of the building, determine the low parameters of habitability existing.

With regard to sanitation, Spanish cooperation through Convention for the Integrated Development of Guet Ndar had made sanitation one of its fields of action. But with the difficulty of the National Sanitation Office of Senegal, it is reorienting its actions and working today in the creation of a center for fish processing of Guet Ndar.

Thus, at Guet Ndar there are three non-functional pipelines in the neighborhood as well as a section of functional pipeline. The largest part of the area surrounding the neighborhood is a non-functional buried sewage pipeline, which was carried out 10 years ago by an association of companies. As a result of the completion of the work, National Sanitation Office of Senegal noted a failure in the circulation of the water and refused to accept the work. Apparently, there was a poor estimate of the budget estimates and the necessary interventions. Although the real reasons for the non-functionality of the network are still ignored by institutions and inhabitants, it could be an execution of sloping sections or movements of land.

The second existing network is an obsolete traditional pipe section, which is kept separately on one of the streets and ends up in the river. It is attached to the facades of the dwellings and is formed by canals 80 centimeters deep, approximately, in a poor state of conservation.

The third network consists of invisible factory wells from the surface, with an ignored trace. It is parallel to the dwellings, but it is not known if it is in the whole neighborhood. Some wells were located after opening of the entames.

VII. RESTRUCTURING OF SPACE

The Guet Ndar area must benefit from a restructuring project to guarantee minimum living conditions. This implies the implementation of management tools involving inter-institutional cooperation and an upgrading of the quality of the spaces.

This work will be done in several stages with documents to be put forward for corrections and to improve with the will of the different partners for a success of the project. This will involve:

- A development plan with new or improved roads. It is necessary to clear the tracks to release the space necessary for the realization of equipment that are defects.
- A plan for the relocation of the surplus population with a preliminary study of the existing zones in relation to the municipal land reserves.
- A study on the impact of the project on population and the environment.
- Proposals for development activities, in particularly in the fisheries sector, which occupies the majority of the population and retraining in other trades.

All studies must take into account the general documents, namely the Master Plan of Urban Planning and the Community Development Plan.

Future work can be done in the image of a city contract or even a neighborhood contract. The city contract is a contractual framework for the city's policy created to simplify and standardize the rehabilitation of disadvantaged neighborhoods by creating synergy between the actions of the State and local actions.

The neighborhood contract that of Guet Ndar; precisely; falls within this framework and will be rather a multi-year commitment between the municipality of Saint-Louis and its partners and the district of Guet Ndar to implement urban social development at the neighborhood scale.

The basic concept will be the participation of the population as well as for the city contract whose aim is to integrate the neighborhood in the city.

In order to claim efficient and adequate functioning of sanitation; There is an urgent need to carry out awareness-raising campaigns against the Guet Ndar population in order to popularize the adoption of new behaviors in the face of this unsanitary situation. This is in line with the Convention's logic of action for the implementation of the sanitation infrastructure project and support for the productive fishing sector. These awareness-raising actions will have to be implemented through the following fields:

- Use of private and public sanitation with the assimilation of technical conditions of use; the encouragement of the social compromise towards the private sanitation solution and the appropriation of the network by the population and the compromise for maintenance.

- Cleanliness of streets and public spaces with discussions and training on the cleanliness of streets and its contribution to safe habitat but also the proper functioning of collection systems and storm water piping.

- Citizenship with discussions; Training and assimilation of some standards of good behavior for a better management of the public area of the neighborhood.

- Garbage collection for clean streets. This can be done within an agreement with partners through the implementation of a garbage collection system in the neighborhood with the participation of the beneficiary population. Within the framework of the General Sanitation Plan of Saint-Louis; the activities will coordinate with the public bodies and organizations involved; by proposing a solution for the sustainable collection of residues.

CONCLUSION

Given the current state of the neighborhood and the urgency of the solutions, it is necessary to update the projects made on Guet Ndar and to work for simple measures of rehabilitation of the neighborhood in collaboration with the population through the neighborhood council, interface with the municipality, which advocates participatory development with "better management of structures, goods and actions resulting from planning, fruits of their decision".

Thus, public awareness and involvement are necessary for a better approach to the field and needs assessment (in this area, the work will be facilitated by the neighborhood council, which is a relay for local development to mobilize stakeholders at the grassroots level and fostering an ongoing dialogue between the populations, the municipality and the development partners.

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Biography

Birthplace: Ngaye-Ngaye, Senegal

Date of Birth: February 14, 1977

- 2012-Current: Ph.D in Urban Planning in the College of Architecture and Urban Planning, Tongji University, Shanghai, China.
- 2009: Master's degree in Planning, Decentralization and Local Development, Cheikh Anta Diop University, Dakar, Senegal.
- 2007: Master's degree in Land Use Planning, Gaston Berger University, Saint-Louis, Senegal.
- 1998: Graduated Mame Cheikh Mbaye High school, Tambacounda, Senegal.

In 2007, he was a SUPERVISOR in the National Survey on "Women's Rights and Access to Land: A Citizen to Conquer" by the Gender and Society Study and Research Group (GSSRG) at the Gaston Berger University in Saint -Louis.

In August 2009, he participated in the development of the Local Development Plan as a RESEARCHER for the Rural Community of Ndiebene Gandiol (Region of Sain-Louis). In August 2009, he did a four-month internship at the Saint-Louis Communal Development Agency in the Urban Planning Department. During this internship, he worked as an URBAN PLANNER for the development and restructuring of the districts of Guet Ndar. At the same time, he participated in the International Urban Workshop; Saint-Louis 2030: New African Metropolis. The theme was: In response to new environmental challenges, what strategy will ensure dynamic, balanced and sustainable development? In January 2010, he worked under the Mayor of Saint-Louis, as PROJECT MANAGER of decentralized cooperation projects. In January 2011, he worked as the MANAGER of the Private Parking and the Operations of Pound of the Municipality of Saint-Louis.

In 2010, Dr.Diop took part in the students and young professionals urban workshop with 6 other specialists from different countries and published "Saint-Louis 2030: New African Metropolis" in Les Ateliers Urban planning and Development journal. The theme was: In response to new environmental challenges, what strategy will ensure dynamic, balanced and sustainable development?